

Mechanistic aspects of ligand substitution on *cis*-diaqua-chloro-tris-(dimethyl sulfoxide)-ruthenium(II) complex by some amino acids in aqueous medium

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Abstract : The kinetics of the interaction between *cis*-[RuCl(Me₂SO)₃(H₂O)₂]⁺ and some selected amino acids such as glycine (L¹H), L-valine (L²H) and L-leucine (L³H) have been studied spectrophotometrically as a function of [substrate complex], [ligand] and temperature at a particular pH (5.0), where the substrate complex exists predominantly as a diaqua species (in aqueous solution) and ligands as the zwitter ions. The reactions were found to proceed via two distinct consecutive steps : first one is [ligand] dependent but the second is [ligand] independent. The rate constants for the processes are : $k_1 \sim 10^{-3} \text{ s}^{-1}$ and $k_2 \sim 10^{-5} \text{ s}^{-1}$. The activation parameters, calculated from Eyring plots suggest an associative mode of activation for the interactions. From the temperature dependence of the outer sphere association equilibrium constants, the thermodynamic parameters were also calculated, which gives a negative ΔG^0 value at all temperatures studied, supporting the spontaneous formation of an outer sphere association complex.

Keywords : Ligand substitution, amino acids, *cis*-[RuCl(Me₂SO)₃(H₂O)₂]⁺, kinetics.

Introduction

cis-Pt(NH₃)₂Cl₂ (*cis*-platin) is well known as an anti-tumor drug^{1,2}. However, there are still difficulties related to its use, because of numerous side effects and its toxicity. Several methods have been developed during the past ten years which have considerably reduced these side effects. *Cis*-platin is not very soluble in water and tends to hydrolyze at neutral pH. Replacement of chloro ligands by carboxylate groups in carboplatin³, *cis*-diammine(1,1-cyclobutanedicarboxylate)-platinum(II), reduces the toxicity and increases the solubility in water. Among the platinum family elements, ruthenium has been successfully developed and tumor-inhibiting ruthenium complexes have been investigated in order to gain insight into their biological activities⁴⁻¹⁰. The tumor inhibiting activities of ruthenium complexes, such as [Ru(NH₃)₃Cl₃], *cis*-[Ru(NH₃)₄Cl₂]Cl or *cis*-[RuCl₂(Me₂SO)₄], have been known for quite some time¹¹. The complex *cis*-[Ru^{II}Cl₂(Me₂SO)₄] presents lower toxicity¹² than *cis*-platin and also, better antitumor activity *in vivo* (against Ehrlich ascites carcinoma, Lewis lung carcinoma, B16 melanoma, and MCa mammary carcinoma). Despite extensive studies on N-heterocyclic carbenes (NHC) complexes in organometallic chemistry and catalysis, only a restricted

array of biomedical applications have been reported so far for silver, gold, palladium, copper, ruthenium, and rhodium derivatives, mainly for antimicrobial and antitumor purposes^{13,14}. The interesting nature is also reflected in the fascinating field of kinetics of ligand substitution and diverse types of mechanism proposed¹⁵⁻²¹ thereof. Both associative and dissociative mode of activation is proposed depending on the ligands and reaction conditions. Anation reactions are particularly important in a preparative sense since it includes replacement of an important ligand like H₂O. Ruthenium complexes are becoming more and more popular due to their developed synthetic chemistry and great flexibility to fine-tune properties by modifications to the ligand sphere.

In this paper we extend our investigations to the anation of *cis*-[RuCl(Me₂SO)₃(H₂O)₂]⁺ (**1**) by three amino acids, viz. glycine (L¹H), L-valine (L²H) and L-leucine (L³H) to get a better understanding of the kinetic behavior of ruthenium(II).

Results and discussion

UV-Vis spectral study :

The absorption spectra of the resultant solutions were recorded using an aqueous ligand solution of appropriate

molarities in the reference cell, and it was found that the maximum absorbance difference between the products and the substrate complex, $[\text{RuCl}(\text{Me}_2\text{SO})_3(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]^+$ (1) was observed at 220 nm (Fig. 1).

IR spectra :

The IR spectrum in the KBr disc shows strong bands at $3454, 1616 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ together with medium bands at 2920 cm^{-1} and 684 cm^{-1} . The presence of strong stretching

Fig. 1. Absorbance differences between substrate complex and products : (1) $[\text{RuCl}(\text{Me}_2\text{SO})_3(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]^+ = 1.0 \times 10^{-4} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$; (2) $[\text{RuCl}(\text{Me}_2\text{SO})_3(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]^+ = 1.0 \times 10^{-4} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $[\text{L}^1\text{H}] = 3.0 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$; (3) $[\text{RuCl}(\text{Me}_2\text{SO})_3(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]^+ = 1.0 \times 10^{-4} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $[\text{L}^2\text{H}] = 3.0 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$; (4) $[\text{RuCl}(\text{Me}_2\text{SO})_3(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]^+ = 1.0 \times 10^{-4} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $[\text{L}^3\text{H}] = 3.0 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$; pH = 5.0.

The relative λ_{max} positions of LH substituted products are 208, 223 and 230 nm for L^1H , L^2H and L^3H respectively in aqueous medium. A sharp lower energy shift of λ_{max} position in going from complexed L^1H to L^3H reflects a trend in weak donicity.

Job's measurement :

The product composition was checked by Job's method of continuous variation as shown in Fig. 2 and was found to have a 1 : 1 metal : ligand ratio in the product.

Now complex (1) and glycine (L^1H) were mixed in 1 : 1 molar ratio at pH 5.0 and a yellowish product was obtained. Then the product is characterized by IR, ESI-MS and conductance measurements.

Fig. 2. Job's plot : $[\text{RuCl}(\text{Me}_2\text{SO})_3(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]^+ = 1.0 \times 10^{-4} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $[\text{L}^1\text{H}] = 1.0 \times 10^{-4} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, pH = 5.0.

Fig. 3. ESI-mass spectra of the products with L¹H, L²H and L³H respectively.

band at $\sim 3454\text{ cm}^{-1}$ indicates the presence of free -OH groups or the product is hydrated. The band at 2920 cm^{-1} is assigned to $\nu(\text{C-H})$ stretching frequency. The asymmetric COO^- stretching frequency (ν_{asym}) of the amino acids occurs at $1580\text{--}1660\text{ cm}^{-1}$ when the group is coordinated to metals, whereas a non-coordinated COO^- group has the $\nu_{\text{asym}}(\text{COO}^-)$ stretching at lower frequency. The band at 1616 cm^{-1} is therefore due to the coordinated COO^- group. The peak at 684 cm^{-1} is attributed to Ru-N bond formation.

Fig. 4. Plausible structures of the molecular ion peaks from the ESI-mass spectra ($m/z \sim 448$, $m/z \sim 490$ and $m/z \sim 521$ for the products with L^1H , L^2H and L^3H respectively).

Mass spectral analysis :

It is clear from the first spectrum (product with L^1H) that the ion at $m/z \sim 448$ has become the molecular ion species in the mixture solution and this is attributed to $[(\text{Ru}) + (3\text{DMSO}) + (\text{Cl}) + (\text{L}^1\text{H}-\text{H}^+)]$. The second spectrum (product with L^2H) reveals that the ion at $m/z \sim 490$ has become the molecular ion species in the mixture solution and this is attributed to $[(\text{Ru}) + (3\text{DMSO}) + (\text{Cl}) + (\text{L}^2\text{H}-\text{H}^+)]$. And the third spectrum (product with L^3H) reveals that the ion at $m/z \sim 521$ has become the molecular ion species in the mixture solution and this is attributed to $[(\text{Ru}) + (3\text{DMSO}) + (\text{Cl}) + (\text{L}^3\text{H}-\text{H}^+) + (\text{H}_2\text{O})]$ (Fig. 3). The precursor ions are shown in Fig. 4.

Conductance measurements :

The conductance measurement also helps us to assign the product formation. As with the progress of the reaction (complex and glycine (L^1H)) were mixed in 1 : 1 molar ratio at pH 5.0 and a light yellowish liquid product was obtained; the conductance of the product at $t = 0$ is $58\ \mu\text{S}$, and after the completion of the reaction conduc-

tance is $74\ \mu\text{S}$, there is release of H^+ ion (vide mechanism section).

The two dissociation constants of glycine are $[\text{pK}_1(-\text{COOH})]$ 2.34 and $[\text{pK}_2(-\text{NH}_3^+)]$ 9.60 at $25\ ^\circ\text{C}$. Hence at the experimental pH (5.0), glycine exists as dipolar ion, which refer to following dissociation process;

pK values with references and product compositions of the selected amino acids are given in the next table :

Ligand	(Ref.)	Structures	Metal : Ligand
Glycine (L^1H)			
$\text{pK}_1 = 2.34$			
$\text{pK}_2 = 9.60$	(22)		1 : 1
L-Valine (L^2H)			
$\text{pK}_1 = 2.32$			
$\text{pK}_2 = 9.62$	(22)		1 : 1
L-Leucine (L^3H)			
$\text{pK}_1 = 2.36$			
$\text{pK}_2 = 9.60$	(22)		1 : 1

Kinetic studies :

The progress of the reaction was followed by measuring the decrease in absorbance at 220 nm , where the absorbance differences between the substrate and the product complexes are maximum. The plot of $\ln(A_t - A_\infty)$ versus time indicates that the reaction is not a single step process, a two-step consecutive process may be assumed,

the first step being dependent and the final step is independent on the concentration of ligand. The rate constant for such a process can be evaluated by assuming Scheme :

A is complex (1), B is the intermediate with ligand and C is the final chelated product complex.

The $k_{1(\text{obs})}$ and $k_{2(\text{obs})}$ values were calculated graphically (Figs. 5 and 6) using the method of Weyh and Hamm.

Fig. 5. A typical plot of $\ln(A_t - A_\infty)$ versus time t . $[\text{RuCl}(\text{Me}_2\text{SO})_3(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2^+] = 1.0 \times 10^{-4} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $[\text{L}^1\text{H}] = 3.0 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $\text{pH} = 5.0$, $\text{temp.} = 50^\circ\text{C}$.

Fig. 6. A typical plot of $\ln \Delta$ versus time t . $[\text{RuCl}(\text{Me}_2\text{SO})_3(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2^+] = 1.0 \times 10^{-4} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $[\text{L}^1\text{H}] = 3.0 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $\text{pH} = 5.0$, $\text{temp.} = 50^\circ\text{C}$.

Calculation of k_1 for $A \rightarrow B$:

The $k_{1(\text{obs})}$ values are collected in Table 1. The procedure of calculations was given in our earlier work²³.

Table 1. $10^3 k_{1(\text{obs})}$ values for different ligand concentrations at different temperatures

Ligands	Temp. (°C)	$10^3 [\text{Ligand}] \text{ (mol dm}^{-3}\text{)}$				
		1.00	2.00	3.00	4.00	5.00
L ¹ H	35	0.99	1.89	2.30	2.79	3.02
	40	1.29	2.29	2.94	3.51	3.89
	45	1.62	2.96	3.67	4.35	4.70
	50	2.00	3.45	4.42	5.26	5.49
L ² H	35	0.94	1.72	2.15	2.70	2.96
	40	1.19	2.10	2.79	3.37	3.77
	45	1.55	2.89	3.56	4.21	4.56
	50	1.98	3.39	4.31	5.12	5.39
L ³ H	35	0.90	1.50	2.08	2.55	2.90
	40	1.17	2.01	2.72	3.20	3.70
	45	1.55	2.71	3.39	4.10	4.49
	50	1.94	3.29	4.20	5.00	5.30

The rate increases with increase in $[\text{ligand}]$ and reaches a limiting value (Fig. 7), which is probable due to the completion of the outer sphere association complex formation. Since the metal ion reacts with immediate environment, further change in $[\text{ligand}]$ beyond the saturation point will not affect the reaction rate and a gradual approach towards limiting rate is observed. At this stage the interchange of the ligands from outer sphere to the inner sphere occurs, i.e. LH attacks the Ru^{II} atom of the substrate complex and forming intermediate.

Fig. 7. Plots of $k_{1(\text{obs})}$ versus $[\text{L}^1\text{H}]$ at different temperatures. A = 35, B = 40, C = 45 and D = 50 °C.

Calculation of k_2 for $B \rightarrow C$:

The $B \rightarrow C$ step is intramolecular ring closure and is

independent of ligand concentration. At a particular temperature the slopes of $\ln(A_t - A_\infty)$ versus time plots at different ligand concentrations were found to be constant in the region where the plot is linear (Fig. 5). For different temperatures, the k_2 values are obtained directly from the limiting slopes and are collected in Table 2.

Table 2. The k_1 , k_2 , K_{EI} values for the substitution reaction between ligands and complex

Ligands	Temp. (°C)	$10^3 k_1$ (s ⁻¹)	K_{EI} (dm ³ mol ⁻¹)	$10^5 k_2$ (s ⁻¹)
L ¹ H	35	7.00	167	5.26
	40	8.27	184	7.39
	45	10.07	193	9.98
	50	10.69	231	11.69
L ² H	35	6.52	170	5.00
	40	8.09	73	7.02
	45	9.85	188	9.48
	50	10.13	243	11.31
L ³ H	35	6.27	166	4.67
	40	7.67	180	6.71
	45	9.27	200	9.00
	50	10.03	239	11.10

Effect of temperature :

Four different temperatures were chosen for study and the results are listed in Table 3. The activation parameters for the step A→B and B→C were evaluated from the linear Eyring plots ($\ln k_1 h/k_B T$ versus $1/T$) (Figs. 9 and 10) and are collected in Table 3.

Table 3 Activation parameters for [Complex 1] by ligands in aqueous medium, pH = 5.0

Ligands	ΔH_1^\ddagger (kJ mol ⁻¹)	ΔS_1^\ddagger (JK ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹)	ΔH_2^\ddagger (kJ mol ⁻¹)	ΔS_2^\ddagger (JK ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹)
L ¹ H	21.6 ± 2.5	-216 ± 8	42.5 ± 2.5	-189 ± 8
L ² H	22.9 ± 4.0	-212 ± 13	43.2 ± 1.5	-186 ± 5
L ³ H	24.2 ± 2.2	-209 ± 7	45.7 ± 0.8	-180 ± 3

The low ΔH^\ddagger values are in support of the ligand participation in the transition state for both the steps. The energy required to break the metal-departing ligand bond is partly compensated by the formation of metal-incoming ligand bond and a lower value of ΔH^\ddagger is observed. The high negative ΔS^\ddagger values suggest a more compact transition state, where both the incoming and departing ligands are attached in the transition state, and this is also in support of the assumption of a ligand participated transition state.

Fig. 8. Plots of $1/k_{1(obs)}$ versus $1/[L^1H]$ at different temperatures. A = 35, B = 40, C = 45 and D = 50 °C.

Fig. 9. Eyring plot for L¹H ($\ln k_1 h/k_B T$ versus $1/T$) for the step A → B ($R = 0.98685 \pm 0.03384$).

Mechanism and conclusion :

The interaction of glycine, L-valine and L-leucine with the title ruthenium complex proceeds via two distinct consecutive steps ($k_1 \sim 10^{-3} \text{ s}^{-1}$ and $k_2 \sim 10^{-5} \text{ s}^{-1}$). First path proceeds via an associative interchange activation and the second step is the ring closure. At the outset of first path outer sphere association complex results, this is stabi-

Fig. 10. Eyring plot for L^1H ($\ln k_2/k_B T$ versus $1/T$) for the step $B \rightarrow C$ ($R=0.99661 \pm 0.0335$).

lized through H-bonding and is followed by an interchange from the outer sphere to the inner sphere complex. The outer sphere association equilibrium constants, a measure of the extent of H-bonding for each step at different temperatures are evaluated. From the temperature dependence of the K_{E1} the thermodynamic parameters are also calculated $\Delta H_1^0 = 13.6 \pm 3.6$ kJ mol $^{-1}$, $\Delta S_1^0 = 159 \pm$

temperature studied, have a negative magnitude which is once again in favor of the spontaneous formation of an outer sphere association complex.

Here in the product five membered ring is formed. After studying IR spectra, it was seen that $-\text{COO}^-$ is involved in complexation through O^- centre and $-\text{NH}_2$ centre also involved. As the electron density on O^- is greater than that of amide N centre, O^- follows k_1 path and N follows k_2 path. After k_1 path $-\text{NH}_3^+$ releases one proton and then completes ring closing process.

From a comparison of the amino acids used, it can be concluded that the variation in size, bulkiness and electronic effect of the entering amino acids reflects their properties as nucleophiles. The reactivity of selected amino acids follows the order : L-leucine < L-valine < glycine. The sensitivity of the reaction rate towards donor properties of the entering amino acids are in the line with that expected for an associative mode of activation. Due to the higher steric effect, the reactivity of the amino acid, L-leucine decreases which reflected in the rate constant values.

A plausible mechanism is shown as below :

12 JK $^{-1}$ mol $^{-1}$ (for L^1H), $\Delta H_1^0 = 15.5 \pm 7.7$ kJ mol $^{-1}$, $\Delta S_1^0 = 153 \pm 24$ JK $^{-1}$ mol $^{-1}$ (for L^2H) and $\Delta H_1^0 = 17.0 \pm 3.5$ kJ mol $^{-1}$, $\Delta S_1^0 = 148 \pm 11$ JK $^{-1}$ mol $^{-1}$ (for L^3H). ΔG^0 values, calculated for the first step at all

Experimental

The reactant *cis*-[Ru(Me $_2$ SO) $_4$ Cl $_2$] was prepared and characterized according to the method reported by Evans *et al.*²⁴. RuCl $_3 \cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$ was purchased from Arora Matthey

Limited and dimethyl sulfoxide was E. Merck, India supplied. Amino acids used were purchased from Sisco Research Laboratories. Milli-Q water was used to prepare

UV2450 spectrophotometer attached to a thermoelectric cell temperature controller (Model TCC 240A, accuracy ± 0.1). The conventional mixing technique was followed

Scheme 2. Chemical behavior of *cis*-[Ru(Me₂SO)₄Cl₂] in aqueous medium.

all the kinetic solutions. All the chemicals used were of AR quality. The substrate complex [RuCl(Me₂SO)₃(H₂O)₂]⁺ (1) was prepared *in situ* by dissolving the above reactant complex in the aqueous solution²⁵.

Cis-[Ru(Me₂SO)₄Cl₂] once dissolved in water, immediately releases the O-bonded dimethyl sulfoxide molecule²⁴.

UV-Vis spectral study :

The product (2) of the reaction between the substrate complex and glycine was prepared by mixing different molar ratios of reactants, viz. 1 : 1, 1 : 2 and 1 : 3 at pH 5.0 and thermostating the mixture at 50 °C for 24 h. The spectral study was done in a Shimadzu UV-Vis spectrophotometer (UV-2450), attached to a thermoelectric cell temperature controller (Model TCC-240A with an accuracy of ± 0.1 °C).

IR spectra :

IR spectra (KBr disc, 4000–400 cm⁻¹) were measured in Perkin-Elmer FTIR model RX1 Infrared spectrophotometer. Complex (1) and adenosine were mixed in 1 : 2 molar ratios at pH 5.0 and a yellowish product was obtained.

Mass spectral analysis :

ESI-mass spectra were recorded using a micromass Q-Tof microTM mass spectrometer in positive ion mode.

Conductance measurements :

Conductance values were recorded using Systronics Conductivity meter 304.

Kinetic studies :

Kinetic measurements were carried out on a Shimadzu

and pseudo-first order conditions were employed throughout. The pHs of the solutions were adjusted with *p*-toluene sulfonic acid/NaOH and measured with a Sartorius pH meter (Model PB11) with an accuracy of ± 0.01 .

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